

Employee Performance Management and Performance of Food Beverage Manufacturing Firms of Enugu State

Authored by

Everist Onyehuluchukwu Eneh PhD^a, Ogbuke, John Chukwu PhD^b & Okwor, Evaristus Onyeaghana^c

^aDepartment of Business Administration, Enugu State University of Science and Technology

^bDepartment of Marketing, Enugu State University of Science and Technology

^cDepartment of Business Administration, Enugu State University of Science and Technology

Abstract

The study evaluated the employee performance management practices and performance of food beverage manufacturing firms of Enugu State. The specific objectives were to: examine the relationship between engaged employees and the profitability and evaluate the relationship between identification of talent and output of food manufacturing firms of Enugu State. The area of the study was the SMEs in Enugu State. The study used the descriptive survey design approach. The primary source of data was the administration of questionnaire. A total population of 911 selected staff of the study organisations. The adequate sample size of two hundred and Seventy (270) using Freund and William's statistic formula at 5 percent margin of error. Two hundred and twenty-eight (228) staff returned the questionnaire and accurately filled. The hypotheses were analyzed using Pearson correlation coefficient (r). The findings indicated there was significant positive relationship between Engaged employees and the profitability $r(95, n=228), = .453 < .985, P < .05$ and there was significant positive relationship between identification of talent and output of food manufacturing firms of Enugu State $r(95, n=228), = .416 < .971, P < .05$. The study concluded that engaged employees and talent had significant positive relationship with the profitability and output of food beverage manufacturing firms of Enugu State. The study recommended among others that Learning and development, and employee career management, should be leveraged on by the management by concentrating on the coaching and training programs and job rotation so that firms can achieve sustainable organizational performance.

Keywords: Employee Performance Management; Food Beverage Manufacturing Firms; Enugu State

Introduction

Employee performance is critical to the overall success of the company. Business leaders need to understand the key benefits of employee performance so that they can develop consistent and objective methods for evaluating employees. Performance is a critical factor in organizational success, helping to also improve overall productivity, profitability, and employee morale. By assessing employee performance regularly, companies can identify areas that need improvement, provide support and training to employees, and ensure that everyone is working towards the same goals (Leonard, 2019). Human resources as one of the resources in the organization play an important role in the successful achievement of organizational goals. In the development of human resources, the performance of an employee in a company is needed to achieve employee performance itself and also for the success of the company. Improving the performance of these employees is not only beneficial for the company, but also for the employees themselves. Because with good performance theoretically can achieve a better level of employee career development (Siahaan, Gultom, and Lumbanraja, 2016).

Employee management is an essential function within a company both traditionally, and more importantly, strategically. Satisfied employees form positive reference to the employer and thus increase its attractiveness for potential job seekers and strengthen its competitive position in the market. Performance management process is a collaborative, communication-based process where employees and management work together to plan, monitor and review the employee's objectives, long-term goals, job trajectory and comprehensive contribution to the company. This process is continual, with regular sessions where both management and employees have the opportunity to give and receive feedback (Valamis, 2023). *Management* is the *process* during which responsible *employees* within an *organisation* get the job done working together with others. Management of the company does not often know opinions of own employees and underestimates dependence between satisfaction of employees and total successfulness of the company in the market. Indeed (2023) asserts that business organizations can structure and use their leadership and resources in a variety of ways to set and achieve goals. They use organizational management to give employees direction and encourage them to work toward a common objective. By understanding how this strategy works, it can help organizations operate efficiently and achieve its vision. Employee involvement connote the idea of allowing employees to participate in decisions that affect them, increasing their autonomy and control of their work, delegating more authority and responsibility to them, in other to make them more committed, motivated and satisfied with their jobs in an organization (Obiekwe, Zeb-Obipi & Ejo-Orusa, 2019). Employees therefore, are success lubricant for organizations. Any organization which sees employees as automations or mere cog in a wheel will never realize their full potentials but will continuously struggle for survival in the face of competitions and challenges

Statement of Problem

A motivated and high performing individual is more likely to be regarded as important by an organisation than an unengaged and demotivated individual. Every employee who has high work discipline will try to carry out his work to the fullest and provide high productivity in accordance with the company's expectations. In our current intense competitive environments, allowing employees to be involved in decision-making and problem solving become an important factor in organizational innovativeness, effectiveness and a reliable strategy to gain competitive advantage over rivals; particularly when competent and serious-minded employees are involved in strategic organizational actions.

Employee involvement is not an end to itself but a means. As such, organizations should put in place other necessary policies capable of generating the needed employee involvement. Employee performance in organizations is often hindered when there is poor engagement of employees and identification of their talent in the organisation. This leads to discouragement of the employees and exhibition of poor performance. To be successful, companies must be flexible to allow an adjustment in production and resources to meet changing markets and customer demands. They must, therefore, have employees that possess the skill and training required to perform a range of different tasks.

Forward looking organizations thus, are constantly in search for reliable strategies that will help them navigate through these mucky waters, and create a viable strong competitive edge over their rivals. First and foremost, challenges facing employees in the organization should be tackled and avoided as it can highly affect not only the

employees but also the organization at large there by resulting to poor profitability and meager output in the organization. The performance management process, when done correctly, is designed to fix those problems in the workplace, setting employees up for success in achieving both their goals and overall company objectives. This has necessitated for the study on the employee performance management practices and performance of food beverage manufacturing firms of Enugu State

Objectives of the Study

The main objective of the study was to evaluate the employee performance management practices and performance of food beverage manufacturing firms of Enugu State. The specific objectives were to:

- i. Examine the relationship between engaged employees and the profitability of food beverage manufacturing firms of Enugu State.
- ii. Evaluate the relationship between identification of talent and output of food manufacturing firms of Enugu State.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study

- i. What is the relationship between Engaged employees and the profitability of food beverage manufacturing firms of Enugu State?
- ii. What is the relationship between identification of talent and output of food manufacturing firms of Enugu State?

Statement of Hypotheses

The following Hypotheses guided the study

- i. There is no significant relationship between Engaged employees and the profitability of food beverage manufacturing firms of Enugu State.
- ii. There is no significant relationship between identification of talent and output of food manufacturing firms of Enugu State.

Review of the Related Literature

Conceptual Review

Employee

Employees are the individual who was hired by an employer to do a specific job. The employee is hired by the employer after an application and interview process results in his or her selection as an employee. This selection occurs after the applicant is found by the employer to be the most qualified of their applicants to do the job for which they are hiring (Heathfield, 2021). This is always a risk that the employer takes because they need to employ people who can do the work required to perform a particular job. Most employees who work in service or product creating roles have a narrow range of potential salary offers since their jobs are defined with a salary range and benefits in mind. An employee is hired for a specific job or to provide labor in the service of someone else (the employer). When an individual begins a long-term working relationship with a business, that person usually becomes an employee, though there are exceptions (Murray, 2020). Employees have special protections, as well as certain obligations, compared to other kinds of workers.

Performance

Performance is described as a subjective perception of reality, which explains the multitude of critical reflections on the concept and its measuring instruments. The term performance emerged in the mid-nineteenth century and was first used in defining the results to a sporting contest. In the twentieth century, the concept has evolved and developed a series of definitions that were meant to encompass the widest sense of what is perceived through

performance (Ion and Criveanu, 2016). Performance means the actual output or results of an organization as measured against its intended outputs (or goals and objectives). Performance involves analyzing an organization's performance against its objectives and goals. In other words, organizational performance comprises real results or outputs compared with intended outputs. Performance is a relation between cost (operation cost the organization) and the value of benefits obtained (Cosmin, Gheorghe and Raluca, 2012).

Management

Management is said to be the ability of planning, decision making, organizing, leading, motivation and controlling the human resources, financial, physical, and information resources of an organization to reach its goals efficiently and effectively (Dill, 2021). Management (or managing) is the administration of organizations, whether they are a business, a non-profit organization, or a government body. It is the art and science of managing resources of the business. Management includes the activities of setting the strategy of an organization and coordinating the efforts of its employees (or of volunteers) to accomplish its objectives through the application of available resources, such as financial, natural, technological, and human resources (Dubrin, 2009). "Run the business" and "Change the business" are two concepts that are used in management to differentiate between the continued delivery of goods or services and adapting of goods or services to meet the changing needs of customers.

Practices

Practices are actions or activities that are repeatable, regular, and recognizable in a given cultural context. In the 1970s and 1980s, practice and practices came to be seen as the object of theorization in certain branches of critical sociology and cultural anthropology. Practice is repeating of an act, behavior, or sequence of activities, frequently to better performance or learn an ability or trade (Sam, 2023). Practice theories, in general, seek to integrate objectivist theories of society (such as structuralism, functionalism, or Marxism) with theories that view social life as the contingent outcome of decisions, actions, and interpretations of competent (albeit not fully conscious) social actors. Practice thus produces subjectivity (both in the sense of identity and the sense of subjection), simultaneously constituting and limiting social subjects. How well one improves with practice depends on several factors, such as the frequency it is engaged in, and the type of feedback that is available for improvement.

Employee Performance Management Practices

Employees at all levels of organizational hierarchy should endeavor to invest in personal skill acquisition and development in order to acquire the necessary competencies and knowledge that will make them relevant and ready to be actively involved in various organizational activities. Employee performance management is the continuous process of improving performance by setting individual and team goals which are aligned to the strategic goals of the organization, planning performance to achieve the goals, reviewing and assessing progress, and developing the knowledge, skills, and abilities of people (Review, 2023). An effective performance management system should prioritise employee recognition and reward. Employees should feel valued and appreciated for the work they do and the effort they put in. Planning, coaching, reviewing and rewarding are the employee management processes. Each step is equally important, and together forms the backbone of a company's performance management process (Valamis, 2023).

Engaged Employees

Employee engagement affects just about every important aspect of your organization, including profitability, revenue, customer experience, employee turnover, and more. Employee engagement is the strength of the mental and emotional connection employees feel toward the work they do, their teams, and their organization. Employee engagement is appealing to HR because of its immediate benefits in employee retention, recruitment, job satisfaction, and happiness (Ryba, 2021). Engaged employees also known as employee engagement is a fundamental concept in the effort to understand and describe, both qualitatively and quantitatively, the nature of the relationship between an organization and its employees. Employee engagement is a human resources (HR) concept that describes the level of enthusiasm and dedication a worker feels toward their job. Engaged employees care about their work and about the performance of the company, and feel that their efforts make a difference (Smith, Kindness

& Rathburn, 2022). Employee engagement can be critical to a company's success, given its clear links to job satisfaction and employee morale.

Identification of Talent

Determining goals is a critical first step in defining an effective talent. When organizations have a clear understanding of what they want to achieve, they can design an evaluation process that is tailored to those goals. Identification of talent is the approach by an organization to hire, manage, develop and retain the talented employees to flourish. Talent management refers to the commitment of an organization to hire, manage, develop and retain the talented employees to flourish. It comprises all the processes and systems that are linked to retaining and developing an effective and superior workforce (Tutorials, 2022). Talent is a set of unique abilities possessed by individuals. Talent management includes within its fold those individuals who can make a difference to the organization's goals, either through their immediate contribution or in the long run. Talent is a crucial aspect of building a successful organisation. Talent evaluation helps ensure that you hire the right people for the right roles and create a capable, effective workforce aligned with your organisation's goals and needs. A talent is a person who has the aptitude or skill to do something well. In the business context, a talent would be an employee who possesses the potential to drive organisational growth. Workforce (2023) asserts that choosing the right assessment tools is another critical step in defining and identifying a talent in the workplace. There are a wide range of assessment tools available, including cognitive ability tests, personality inventories, situational judgment tests, and more. The specific tools you select should be aligned with the project objectives and the skills and competencies you are seeking to assess. To choose the right assessment tools, it is important to first identify the specific skills or competencies you are looking to assess.

Profitability

Profitability is stated to be the ability of a company to use its resources to generate revenues in excess of its expenses. In other words, this is a company's capability of generating profits from its operations. Profitability is one of four building blocks for analyzing financial statements and company performance as a whole. The other three are efficiency, solvency, and market prospects, (My Accounting course, 2022). Profitability is the degree to which the value of a farm's production exceeds the cost of the resources used to produce it. An absolute measure of profitability is net farm income. If the opportunity costs for the farmer's own labor and capital are subtracted, the remainder is profit and return to management. A positive profit means that the farm has produced crops and livestock that have a greater value than the seed, fertilizer, fuel, labor, feed, and other inputs that were used up in their production, (Edwards, and Duffy, 2014).

Output

Output can be described as the quantity of goods or services produced in a given time period, by a firm, industry, whether consumed or used for further production. The concept of national output is essential in the field of macroeconomics (Paul and William, 2014). Output is the result of an economic process that has used inputs to produce a product or service that is available for sale or use somewhere else (Wikipedia, 2022). Organization output is the balance between all factors of production that will give the maximum output with the smallest effort (Neyna, 2018). It is a metric that is calculated based on the amount of productivity on a project versus the amount of time it takes. Output refers to the total production of goods and services of a whole country over a given period – its gross domestic product.

Conceptual Framework of the Study

Fig 1: Conceptual Framework Model

Source: Researcher, 2023

Theoretical Framework

The study adopted the goal-setting theory and the expectancy theory. The study was anchored on goal-setting theory. The theory proposed that Goal setting involves the development of an action plan designed in order to motivate and guide a person or group toward a goal. In line with the study this theory shows that an organization thrive well when the management state its practices and strategies through which objective can be achieved.

Goal-Setting Theory

The theory was developed by Edwin A. Locke in 1968. Goal setting involves the development of an action plan designed in order to motivate and guide a person or group toward a goal. Goals are more deliberate than desires and momentary intentions. Setting goals means that a person has committed thought, emotion, and behavior towards attaining the goal, in doing so, the goal setter has established a desired future state which differs from their current state thus creating a mismatch which in turn spurs future actions (Michael, Legault and Teper, 2014). Goal setting can be guided by goal-setting criteria (or rules) such as SMART criteria (Grant, 2012). Goal setting is a major component of personal-development and management literature. Studies by Edwin A. Locke and his colleagues, most notably have shown that more specific and ambitious goals lead to more performance improvement than easy or general goals. The goals should be specific, time constrained and difficult. Vague goals reduce limited attention resources. Unrealistically short time limits intensify the difficulty of the goal outside the intentional level and disproportionate time limits are not encouraging (Kayla and Sergent, 2021). As long as the person accepts the goal, has the ability to attain it, and does not have conflicting goals, there is a positive linear relationship between goal difficulty and task performance. The underlying assumptions of the theory are that goals and intentions are cognitive and volitional, and that they serve as the immediate regulators of human action. The goal commitment of theory is that, people perform better when they are committed to achieving certain goals. Through an understanding of the effect of goal setting on individual performance, organizations are able to use goal setting to benefit organizational performance (Edwin and Latham, 2002). Goal Setting Theory explains the mechanisms by which goals influence behavior, and how the latter can be moderated by goal characteristics (difficulty and specificity), the level of commitment, the importance of the goal, levels of self-efficacy, feedback, and task complexity.

Expectancy Theory

Expectancy theory anchored upon objective four of this study, payment of salary supplement has effect on time to service of the institutions of study. In 1964, Victor H. Vroom developed the expectancy theory through his study of the motivations behind decision-making. This theory is relevant to the study of management. The expectancy theory of motivation explains the behavioral process of why individuals choose one behavioral option over the other. This theory explains that individuals can be motivated towards goals if they believe that there is a positive correlation

between efforts and performance, the outcome of a favorable performance will result in a desirable reward, a reward from a performance will satisfy an important need, and/or the outcome satisfies their need enough to make the effort worthwhile.

Vroom introduced three variables within the expectancy theory which are valence (V), Expectancy (E) and instrumentality (I). The three elements are important behind choosing one element over another because they are clearly defined: effort-performance expectancy (E>P expectancy), performance-outcome expectancy (P>O expectancy) (Rao, 2000). Expectancy theory proposes that an individual will behave or act in a certain way because they are motivated to select a specific behavior over others due to what they expect the result of that selected behavior will be (Oliver, 1974). In essence, the motivation of the behavior selection is determined by the desirability of the outcome. However, at the core of the theory is the cognitive process of how an individual processes the different motivational elements. This is done before making the ultimate choice. The outcome is not the sole determining factor in making the decision of how to behave. This theory emphasizes the needs for organizations to relate rewards directly to performance and to ensure that the rewards provided are those rewards deserved and wanted by the recipients (Montana and Charnov, 2008).

Empirical Review

The relationship between Engaged Employees and the Profitability

Mariza (2016) conducted a study on the impact of employees' motivation and engagement on employees' performance of manufacturing companies in Jakarta Indonesia. Empirical research has been conducted on employee's perception of the impact of employees' motivation and engagement on employees' performance in manufacturing companies in Jakarta Indonesia. The purpose of this paper is to gain better understanding on the effective approach to improve employee performance by increasing motivation and engagement of employees in the manufacturing companies. The higher motivation and stronger engagement, can lead to higher satisfaction of the employees and stronger loyalty to the company. This study examines three hypotheses, and empirical research has been conducted in manufacturing companies in Jakarta. Data collection has been collected through surveys and interviews directly to the respondents (the plant head, senior managers and employees in manufacturing companies). This research involved 184 employees as respondent from 4 manufacturing companies in Jakarta, Indonesia. The research method is field survey with convenient sampling and interviews with some senior managers. The data are analyzed by Structural Equation Modeling (SEM), Lisrel program. The findings of research are: (a) Motivation positively and significantly effect on employee performance directly and indirectly through engagement as intervening variable; (b) Motivation positively and significantly effect on employee engagement; (c) Engagement positively and significantly effect on employee performance. However, the constraints of this research are: (a) characterized by cross sectional and perceptual analyzes; (b) the location all of the company involved is in Jakarta. The managerial implication of this research is that they need to improve and coordinate policies, rules, procedures related to the contents of motivation better than the method how to engage of the employees, in order to sustain high motivation. Motivation is basic approach and basic reason for employees to join, stay and work effective. Based on that reasons management must to know and understand the effective way to strengthen their motivation. Even the engagement of employees is hard or difficult to build but effectively impacted to employees' performance. Management approach to emphasize on employees' orientation is effective as one of strategies to create positive engagement of the manufacturing company in Indonesia in this time being. The theoretical implications of this research are that motivation at manufacturing company is one of the approaches to build the engagement and as positive method to improve the employee performance, not the other way around. Engagement is intangible assets and fragile, which is part of human resource approach to be given attention as it has positive implication to performance and sustainable growth of the company.

Orji and Tamunomiebi (2020) conducted a study on Employee Dedication and Organizational Performance of Telecommunications Companies in Rivers State, Nigeria. This study examined the relationship between employee dedication and organizational performance of telecommunication companies in Rivers State. A cross sectional survey design was adopted. Primary data was generated through structured questionnaire. The population of the study was 437 employees of the telecommunication (GSM) firms in Port Harcourt. The sample size of 208 was determined using the Taro Yamane's formula for sample size determination. The reliability of the instrument was achieved by

the use of the Cronbach Alpha coefficient with all the items scoring above 0.70. The hypotheses were tested using the Spearman's Rank Order Correlation Coefficient with the aid of Statistical Package for Social Science version 23.0. The tests were carried out at a 95% confidence interval and a 0.05 level of significance. The findings of the study revealed that there is a significant and relationship between employee dedication and organizational performance of telecommunication companies in Rivers State. The study recommends that telecommunication companies should promote activities and policies that will enhance employee dedication which will give them a sense of significance from work, feeling enthusiastic and proud about the given job, and feeling inspired and challenged by the job.

Eke, Anagha, and Dickson (2021) conducted a study on the effect of capital allowance on manufacturing companies in Enugu State Nigeria. This study examined the effect of capital allowance on manufacturing companies in Enugu state Nigeria. The study adopted the Survey research design while the primary source of data was the source of data engaged for the purpose of this study. Forty-five Staff members from three accounting units of three manufacturing companies in Enugu state Nigeria were administered copies of the questionnaire. The study tested the research hypotheses with Z test statistical tool with the aid of the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS). Findings from this study revealed that Annual allowance have significant effect on the profitability of manufacturing companies in Enugu state. The study also revealed that initial allowance does not have significant effect on the efficiency of manufacturing companies in Enugu state. The study consequently recommends that all manufacturing companies in Enugu state should endeavor to engage the services of professional Accountants for the purpose of maximum performance which are necessary for its survival and sustainability. It further recommends that, manufacturing companies in Enugu via their competent Accountants and Management should apply for annual and initial allowance as at when due on qualifying capital expenditure of the companies.

Ugwu (2021) carried out a study on the Relationship Between Green Recruitment and Organizational Performance in Food, Beverage and Tobacco Manufacturing Firms in Enugu State. The study evaluated the relationship between green recruitment and organizational performance in food, beverage and tobacco manufacturing firms in Enugu State. The specific objectives were to: examine the relationship between attracting knowledgeable employees and quality service; evaluate the relationship between retaining skilled employees and the profitability and identify the relationship between recruiting innovative employees on the sales volume of food, beverage and tobacco manufacturing firms in Enugu State. The primary sources were personal interview and the administration of questionnaire. The population of the study was 3884 staff. A stratified sampling method was adopted. The adequate sample size of 350 was determined using Freund and William's statistic formula. 316 staff returned the questionnaire and accurately filled. That gave 94 percent response rate. The validity of the instrument was tested using content analysis and the result was good. The reliability was tested using the Pearson correlation coefficient (r). It gave a reliability co-efficient of 0.75 which was also good. Data was presented and analyzed by mean score (3.0 and above agreed while below 3.0 disagreed) and standard deviation using Sprint Likert Scale. The hypotheses were analyzed using Pearson correlation coefficient (r) statistics tool. The findings indicated that There was positive significant relationship between attracting knowledgeable employees and quality service in food, beverage and tobacco manufacturing firms in Enugu State as reported in the probability value of ($r=.397 < 0.975, p<.05$). There was positive significant relationship between retaining skilled employees and the profitability of food, beverage and tobacco manufacturing firms in Enugu State as reported in the probability value of ($r=.841 < 0.901, p<.05$). There was positive significant relationship between recruiting innovative employees and the sales volume of food, beverage and tobacco manufacturing firms in Enugu State ($r = .387 < 0.907, p<.05$). The study concluded that attracting knowledgeable employees, retaining skilled employees and recruiting innovative employees had significant relationship with quality service, profitability and the sales volume of food, beverage and tobacco manufacturing firms in Enugu State.

Onovo, Inyama and Nwoha (2022) conducted a study on the Corporate Characteristics and Environmental Reporting in Nigeria Manufacturing Sector. This study investigates the effect of Corporate Characteristics on Environmental Reporting of Beverage companies in Nigeria. Using company's specific Corporate Characteristics. Firm Age (FA), Firm Size (FS) and Return on Assets (ROA) were used to proxy Corporate Characteristics, while Employee Health & Safety Cost Disclosures (EHSCD), Waste Management & Remediation Cost Disclosure (WMRCD) and Donations & Charity Contribution Cost Disclosures (DCCCD) served as proxies for the dependent variable – financial performance. The study selected all 3 companies out of four (4) quoted Beverage companies in Nigerian Stock Exchange as at 2021. Ex Post Facto research design was adopted and the secondary data were collected from annual reports of sampled

firms from 2010 to 2019 through content analysis. The data were analyzed with descriptive statistics and regression analysis. Eview version 8 was applied in testing the hypotheses. The study showed that Sustainable Firm Age has a significant positive effect on EHSCD with a p – value of 0.0000 and a t – statistical value of 5.1416, while Firm Size has a significant positive effect on WMRCDD with a p – value of 0.0000 and a t – statistical value of 5.1964. The study also reveal that Return on Assets has no significant positive effect on DCCDD with a p – value of 0.1176 and a t – statistical value of 1.6185.

Asogwa, Nwoha and Nwankwo (2023) conducted a study on the Effect of Firm Productivity on Financial Performance of Foods and Beverages Manufacturing Firms in Nigeria. The study investigated the effect of firm productivity on the financial performance of food and beverage manufacturing firms in Nigeria from 2011 to 2020. The specific objectives of the study are: to ascertain the effect of sales growth, sales per employee, and profit per employee on return on assets of foods and beverage manufacturing firms in Nigeria. A sample of eight (8) firms was selected from the fifteen (15) food and beverage manufacturing firms listed on Nigeria Stock Exchange during the period. The data collected from the selected firms were analysed using multiple regression analysis and t-statistics. Results from the study showed that the effect of all the independent variables (sales growth, sales per employee and profit per employee) on the returns on assets of the foods and beverage manufacturing firms are positive and statistically significant. The implication of these findings is that as sales growth, sales per employee and profit per employee increase, the return on assets of the firms also increases and vice versa.

Ugwu, Eneh and Orga (2023) conducted a study on the Effect of Corporate Culture on the Profitability of Food Beverages and Tobacco Manufacturing Firms in South East Nigeria. Corporate Culture defers from one organisation to another and is a system of shared understanding or common beliefs held by members of the same organization. These common beliefs and shared understanding affect the performance and profitability of organizations. Hence, the study evaluated the effect of corporate culture on the profitability of food, beverages and tobacco manufacturing firms in South East Nigeria. The specific objectives were to: examine the effect of learning and development on the increase in revenue; evaluate the effect of communication on the change in productivity and determine the effect of trust on the reduced expenses. The study adopted descriptive survey. The primary source of data was questionnaire. A total population of three hundred and twenty-two (312) staff was used. 273 staff returned the questionnaire. Data was analyzed and Z – test was used to test the hypotheses. Findings showed that Learning and development had positive effect on the increase in revenue, $Z(97, n= 273) = 6.582 < 9.547$. Communication had positive effect on the change in productivity $Z(97, n= 273) = .7.006 < 7.671$. Trusts had positive effect on the reduced expenses $Z(97, n= 273) = .7.671 < 10.107$. The study concluded that learning and development, communication and trust had positive significant effect on the increase in revenue, productivity and reduced expenses.

The relationship between Identification of Talent and Output

Depoo, Urbancova and Smolova (2016) carried out a study on a Strategic talent management in agricultural and forestry companies. In a time of a constant change, a company with high-quality, talented employees not only have an advantage in the competitive environment but it is also a more attractive proposition for the potential employees. It is also a 'great place to work' for the existing employees. The article therefore focuses on the approaches to implementing the strategic talent management which are taken by the agricultural and forestry companies. The paper investigates the position taken regarding the talent management in theory. It is based on the aims of a primary survey, the purpose of which was to develop a deeper understanding of the supporting theoretical concepts underpinning the company approaches to talent. The objective of the work is to identify the main components of the strategic talent management based on the primary survey of companies operating in agriculture and forestry. This is accomplished by evaluating the data obtained from the primary analysis of the methods and approaches used on 101 farms and other agricultural companies. The data comes from the manager surveys for which a single manager represented the given company. The mono-dimensional and multi-dimensional statistics were used to evaluate the data. The results indicate that in 62% of the companies examined are familiar with the principles of the talent management and that the talent management forms part of the mission of the company (48%). A deeper analysis is used to further examine the differences in the approach of the companies included in the study. The paper contains an in-depth discussion of the concept of the strategic talent management, as well as identifying the main processes connected with it. Moreover, the paper presents new research findings by defining and validating the

main attributes of the strategic talent management (TM); additionally, the gap between the awareness of the top management of the talent management concept and its use in practice is found and discussed.

Rezaei and Beyerlein (2018) conducted a study on a Talent development: a systematic literature review of empirical studies. The purpose of this study is to identify and examine findings from empirical research regarding organizations' talent development (TD) strategies, taking into consideration the countries in which the studies were conducted, the TD approach organizations adopted, as well as to recognize the positive outcomes of TD implementation as well as potential issues and challenges. The systematic literature review used Garrard's matrix method to organize the review of publications. It identified 31 empirical articles from the total of 551 publications. Findings The findings indicate that a majority of the studies were conducted in countries other than the US and that they were all published recently, after 2007. The results show that organizations have mostly applied organizational development (OD) interventions at the individual level for developing talented employees, followed by formal training and development (FT&D). Additionally, managerial issues regarding were identified as the most common issue on the way of implementing TD interventions.

Umar and Cross (2018) conducted a study on Talent Management and its Effects on the Competitive Advantage in Organizations. This paper aimed to throw more light on the effects and concept of talent management as one of the recent systems that brought to Human Resources Management and its numerous activities especially in the new era. Additionally, it comes not only to survey the motives behind approving such concept in organizations and companies and the impact on its employees but also to identify the most important strategies of talent management and how to deal with its considered as a competitive advantage for its direct impact on performance level as well as to identify the best ways to invest in talent management because of its effects on reducing the economic cost in the organization by retaining and motivating those talents to implement organization overall strategies. Employee's especially talented ones contribute to the achievement of competitive advantage in their organizations because they innovate in their field and they have the ability to make the right decisions to achieve goals. In details, there are some aspects that reflect the weakness of organizational loyalty causing talented people to leave their organizations; this is due to some repellent factors in their organizations, and the absence of the tools which will work on the employees' development in the organizations so as to enhance the employee's talents for the productivity of the organization.

Aina, and Atan (2020) conducted a study on the Impact of Implementing Talent Management Practices on Sustainable Organizational Performance. As organizations operate in an inexorable marketplace, there are always new and unpredictable difficulties that make managerial roles harder and the achievement of organizational goals and objectives more critical. Recently, the implementation of talent management practices in achieving sustainable organizational performance that will match the firms' operational and strategic goals have been the concern of both academics and practitioners, but the issue has not been exhaustively investigated. Thus, the aim of this study is to investigate the effect of talent management practices on the sustainable organizational performance in real estate companies located in the United Arab Emirates. This paper seeks to make contributions through an empirical evaluation of talent management in the United Arab Emirates. A structured questionnaire was distributed to collect data from a study sample of 306 managers working in real estate companies. The proposed hypotheses were verified by structural equation modeling (SEM). The results of this study show that talent attraction and talent retention had no impact on the sustainable organizational performance, whereas learning and development and career management were found to have significantly positive impacts.

Ezenekwe, (2020) carried out a study on the Effect of Environmental Factors on Firm Productivity in Manufacturing Firms in Anambra State, Nigeria. This work examined the effect of environmental factor on firm's productivity in manufacturing firms in Anambra State, Nigeria. The study specifically is designed to determine the effect of economic, technological and political environment on firm's productivity. Relevant theoretical and empirical literature were reviewed. System Theory was employed as the theoretical framework. The population of the study is one thousand nine hundred and twenty-nine (1929). Descriptive statistics and multiple regression analysis were employed to analyze the data generated. The study found that economic environment; Technological environment has a significant positive effect on firm's productivity. While political environment has a significant negative effect on firm's productivity. The study concludes that environmental factors had a significant positive effect on firm's productivity.

Ugwu and Enudu (2022) carried out a study on a Succession Planning and the Performance of Family-Owned Business in Enugu State. The study evaluated Succession planning and the performance of family-owned business in Enugu State. The specific objectives were to; evaluate the relationship between Innovation investment and the profitability; examine the relationship between mentoring and quality of service and identify the relationship between leadership succession planning and business survival of family-owned business in Enugu State. The total population for the study was one thousand and forty-nine (1432). The sample size of 303 was drawn using Freund and Williams's statistical formula at 5 percent error margin. A descriptive survey design was adopted for the study. Instrument used for data collection was the questionnaire and interviews. A total of three hundred and three (303) copies of the questionnaire were distributed to the respondents from which two hundred and sixty-eight (268) copies were returned and accurately filled. That gave 88 percent response rate. It gave a reliability co-efficient of 0.81 which was also good. Data was presented and analyzed by mean score (3.0 and above agreed while below 3.0 disagreed) and Pearson correlation coefficient (r) was used to test the hypotheses with aid of Special Package for Statistical Software (SPSS). The findings indicated that There was positive significant relationship between Innovation investment and the profitability of family-owned business in Enugu State $r(95, n = 268) = .167 < .928, p < .05$. There was positive significant relationship between mentoring and quality of service of family-owned business in Enugu State $r(95, n = 268) = .798 < .937, p < .05$ and There was positive significant relationship between leadership succession planning and business survival of family-owned business in Enugu State $r(95, n = 268) = .487 < .917, p < .05$. The study concluded that Innovation investment; mentoring and leadership succession planning had positive significant relationship with the profitability, quality of service, and business survival of family. Succession planning is a strategy for passing on leadership roles, often the ownership of a company to an employee or group of employees. Succession planning ensures that businesses continue to run smoothly after a company's most important employees retire and leave the company. Succession planning involves cross-training employees so that they develop skills, company knowledge, and a holistic understanding of the company.

Edeh, Zayed, Perevozova, Kryshstal, and Nitsenko (2022) carried out a study on Talent Management in the Hospitality Sector: Predicting Discretionary Work Behaviour. Hospitality organisations have suffered a lot of setbacks, such as low performance caused by the COVID-19 pandemic, during which most management took drastic decisions to retrench talent, and these decisions have engendered low discretionary work behaviour and low emotional labour display amongst its talent. These maladies would have been averted if talent management practices were implemented effectively by hospitality organisations. It is based on this premise that this study investigates the effect of talent management on discretionary work behaviour in hospitality organisations in Nigeria using a survey research design. A sample frame of 820 was drawn from 60 registered hospitality organisations in the south-eastern part of Nigeria. A sample size of 263 was drawn from the sample frame. Linear regression was employed to analyse the formulated hypotheses with the aid of IBM statistical package for the social sciences version 20.0. The findings of the study show that talent management dimensions have significant effects on discretionary work behaviour in hospitality organisations in Nigeria. The study concludes that talent management measured in terms of talent attraction, talent development and talent retention have significant effects on the indicators of discretionary work behaviour.

Gap in Empirical Review

The few studies reviewed were relevant to the study. Nevertheless, there exists literature gaps which the present study tends to build up. The reviewed studies were conducted in geographical locations different from that of the present study. Also, the reviewed studies were analysed using Structural Equation Modeling (SEM), Spearman's Rank Order Correlation Coefficient, Z test, Regression analysis, multiple regression analysis and t-statistics while the present study will be analysed using Pearson Product moment correlation. Further, these was study specifically on evaluating employee performance management practices whereas the reviewed studies employees' motivation and engagement, Employee Dedication, Green Recruitment and Firm Productivity. However, the present study with the adoption of its object seems to be relevant and also worthy to fill these knowledge gaps.

Methodology

The area of the study comprised of five (5) selected food and beverage manufacturing firms in Enugu state. The choice of the firms was due to high number of staff, Capital base above 10 million naira. The study used the descriptive survey design approach. The primary source of data was the administration of questionnaire. A total population of 911 selected staff of the study organisations. The adequate sample size of two hundred and Seventy (270) using Freund and William's statistic formula at 5 percent margin of error. Two hundred and twenty-eight (228) staff returned the questionnaire and accurately filled. That gave 84 percent response rate. The validity of the instrument was tested using content analysis and the result was good. The reliability was tested using the Pearson correlation coefficient (r). It gave a reliability co-efficient of 0.710 which was also good. Data was presented and analyzed by mean score (3.0 and above agreed while below 3.0 disagreed) and standard deviation using Sprint Likert Scale. The hypotheses were analyzed using Pearson correlation coefficient (r).

Data Presentation and Analyses

Data Presentation

The relationship between Engaged employees and the profitability of food beverage manufacturing firms of Enugu State

Table 1: Responses on the relationship between Engaged employees and the profitability of food beverage manufacturing firms of Enugu State

		5	4	3	2	1	ΣFX	-	SD	Decision
		SA	A	N	DA	SD		X		
1	Retaining top talent ensures income generation in the organisation.	465 93 40.8	200 50 21.9	72 24 10.5	38 19 8.3	42 42 18.4	817 228 100%	3.58	1.530	Agree
2	Engaging employees enhances their satisfaction and increase in productivity	365 73 32.0	200 50 21.9	75 25 11.0	48 24 10.5	56 56 24.6	744 228 100%	3.26	1.590	Agree
3	The engaged workers are committed to their employer	420 84 36.8	236 59 25.9	93 31 13.6	30 15 6.6	39 39 17.1	818 228 100%	3.59	1.465	Agree
4	Effective strategies in place helps create a better work culture and enhance organisational reputation	465 93 40.8	236 59 25.9	42 14 6.1	88 44 19.3	36 18 7.9	867 228 100%	3.72	1.372	Agree
5	There is promotion of connectivity in the organisation with engaged employees.	420 84 36.8	236 59 25.9	93 31 13.6	66 33 14.5	21 21 9.2	836 228 100%	3.67	1.345	Agree
Total Grand mean and standard deviation								3.564	1.4604	

Source: Field Survey, 2023

Table 1, 143 respondents out of 228 representing 62.7 percent agreed that retaining top talent ensures income generation in the organisation with mean score 3.58 and standard deviation of 1.530. Engaging employees enhances their satisfaction and increase in productivity 123 respondents representing 53.9 percent agreed with mean score of 3.26 and standard deviation of 1.590. The engaged workers are committed to their employer 143 respondents representing 62.7 percent agreed with mean score of 3.59 and standard deviation of 1.465. Effective strategies in place helps create a better work culture and enhance organisational reputation 152 respondents representing 66.7

percent agreed with mean score of 3.59 and 1.390. There is promotion of connectivity in the organisation with engaged employees 143 respondents representing 40.3 percent agreed with a mean score of 3.67 and standard deviation 1.345.

The relationship between identification of talent and output of food manufacturing firms of Enugu State

Table 2: Responses on the relationship between identification of talent and output of food manufacturing firms of Enugu State

		5	4	3	2	1	ΣFX	-	SD	Decision
		SA	A	N	DA	SD		X		
1	Increase in confidence and motivation facilities activities in the food and beverage firms	370 74 32.5	360 90 39.5	63 21 9.2	66 33 14.5	10 10 4.4	869 228 100%	3.81	1.167	Agree
2	The level of competitiveness in enhanced with talent identification.	340 68 29.8	360 90 39.5	9 3 1.3	72 36 15.8	31 31 13.6	812 228 100%	3.56	1.408	Agree
3	Achievement of the peak performance in golden as in gold in realized.	340 68 29.8	372 93 40.8	54 18 7.9	84 42 18.4	7 7 3.1	857 228 100%	3.76	1.157	Agree
4	The employees are helped to gain skills and experience in a personalized way.	270 54 23.7	288 72 31.6	117 39 17.1	28 14 6.1	49 49 21.5	752 228 100%	3.30	1.451	Agree
5	The organisation ensures higher capabilities levels and raise the bar for the entire workforce.	470 94 41.2	208 52 22.8	105 35 15.4	78 39 17.1	8 8 3.5	869 228 100%	3.81	1.240	Agree
Total Grand mean and standard deviation								3.648	1.2846	

Source: Field Survey, 2023

Table 2, 164 respondents out of 228 representing 72.0 percent agreed that increase in confidence and motivation facilities activities in the food and beverage firms with mean score 3.81 and standard deviation of 1.167. The level of competitiveness in enhanced with talent identification 158 respondents representing 69.3 percent agreed with mean score of 3.56 and standard deviation of 1.408. Achievement of the peak performance in golden as in gold in realized 161 respondents representing 70.6 percent agreed with mean score of 3.76 and standard deviation of 1.157. The employees are helped to gain skills and experience in a personalized way 126 respondents representing 55.3 percent agreed with mean score of 3.30 and 1.451. The organisation ensures higher capabilities levels and raise the bar for the entire workforce 146 respondents representing 64.0 percent agreed with a mean score of 3.81 and standard deviation 1.240.

Test of Hypotheses

There is no significant relationship between engaged employees and the profitability of food beverage manufacturing firms of Enugu State

Table 3: Pearson correlation of there is no significant relationship between Engaged employees and the profitability of food beverage manufacturing firms of Enugu State

		Correlations				
		Retaining top talent ensures income generation in the organisation.	Engaging employees enhances their satisfaction and increase in productivity	The engaged workers are committed to their employer	Effective strategies in place helps create a better work culture and enhance organisational reputation	There is promotion of connectivity in the organisation with engaged employees.
Retaining top talent ensures income generation in the organisation.	Pearson Correlation	1	.693**	.652**	.694**	.624**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000	.000	.000
	N	228	228	228	228	228
Engaging employees enhances their satisfaction and increase in productivity	Pearson Correlation	.693**	1	.604**	.453**	.593**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.000	.000	.000
	N	228	228	228	228	228
The engaged workers are committed to their employer	Pearson Correlation	.652**	.604**	1	.817**	.985**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000		.000	.000
	N	228	228	228	228	228
Effective strategies in place helps create a better work culture and enhance organisational reputation	Pearson Correlation	.694**	.453**	.817**	1	.802**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000		.000
	N	228	228	228	228	228
There is promotion of connectivity in the organisation with engaged employees.	Pearson Correlation	.624**	.593**	.985**	.802**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000	
	N	228	228	228	228	228

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 3 showed the Pearson correlation matrix on gain commitment has no relationship significance with the improved employee productivity showing the correlation coefficients, significant values and the number of cases. The correlation coefficient shows .453 < .985. This value indicates that correlation is significant at 0.05 level (2 tailed) and implies that there was significant positive relationship between Engaged employees and the profitability of food

beverage manufacturing firms of Enugu State ($r = .453 < .985$). The computed correlations coefficient is greater than the table value of $r = .000$ with at alpha level for a two-tailed test ($r = .453 < .985, p < .05$).

Decision Rule

The decision rule is to accept the null hypothesis if the computed r is less than the tabulated r otherwise reject the null hypothesis.

Decision

Since the computed ($r = .453 < .985$) is greater than the table value of $.000$, we reject the null hypothesis. Therefore, we concluded that there was significant positive relationship between Engaged employees and the profitability of food beverage manufacturing firms of Enugu State ($r = .453 < .985$) as reported in the probability value of ($r = .453 < .985, p < .05$).

There is no significant relationship between identification of talent and output of food manufacturing firms of Enugu State

Table 4 Pearson correlation of there is no significant relationship between identification of talent and output of food manufacturing firms of Enugu State

		Increase in confidence and motivation facilities activities in the food and beverage firms	The level of competitiveness in enhanced with talent identification	Achievement of the peak performance in golden as in gold in realized.	The employees are helped to gain skills and experience in a personalized way.	The organisation ensure higher capabilities levels and raise the bar for the entire workforce.
Increase in confidence and motivation facilities activities in the food and beverage firms	Pearson Correlation	1	.864**	.864**	.442**	.691**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000	.000	.000
	N	228	228	228	228	228
The level of competitiveness in enhanced with talent identification.	Pearson Correlation	.864**	1	.971**	.569**	.621**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.000	.000	.000
	N	228	228	228	228	228
Achievement of the peak performance in golden as in gold in realized.	Pearson Correlation	.864**	.971**	1	.534**	.635**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000		.000	.000
	N	228	228	228	228	228
The employees are helped to gain skills and experience in a	Pearson Correlation	.442**	.569**	.534**	1	.416**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000		.000

personalized way.	N	228	228	228	228	228
The organisation ensure higher capabilities levels and raise the bar for the entire workforce.	Pearson Correlation	.691**	.621**	.635**	.416**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000	
	N	228	228	228	228	228
**. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).						

Table 4 showed the Pearson correlation matrix on there is no significant relationship between identification of talent and output showing the correlation coefficients, significant values and the number of cases. The correlation coefficient shows .416 < .971. This value indicates that correlation is significant at 0.05 level (2 tailed) and implies that there was significant positive relationship between identification of talent and output of food manufacturing firms of Enugu State ($r = .416 < .971$). The computed correlations coefficient is greater than the table value of $r = .000$ with at alpha level for a two-tailed test ($r = .416 < .971, p < .05$).

Decision Rule

The decision rule is to accept the null hypothesis if the computed r is less than the tabulated r , otherwise reject the null hypothesis.

Decision

Since the computed ($r = .453 < .985$) is greater than the table value of .000, we reject the null hypothesis. Therefore, we concluded that there was significant positive relationship between identification of talent and output of food manufacturing firms of Enugu State ($r = .416 < .971$) as reported in the probability value of ($r = .416 < .971, p < .05$).

Discussion of Findings

There was significant positive relationship between Engaged Employees and the Profitability of Food Beverage Manufacturing Firms of Enugu State

Profitability is the degree to which the value of a farm's production exceeds the cost of the resources used to produce it. The result of hypotheses one showed the computed ($r = .453 < .985$) was greater than the table value of .000. Therefore, we concluded that there was significant positive relationship between Engaged employees and the profitability of food beverage manufacturing firms of Enugu State ($r = .453 < .985$) as reported in the probability value of ($r = .453 < .985, p < .05$). Ugwu, Eneh and Orga (2023) conducted a study on the Effect of Corporate Culture on the Profitability of Food Beverages and Tobacco Manufacturing Firms in South East Nigeria. Corporate Culture defers from one organisation to another and is a system of shared understanding or common beliefs held by members of the same organization. These common beliefs and shared understanding affect the performance and profitability of organizations. Hence, the study evaluated the effect of corporate culture on the profitability of food, beverages and tobacco manufacturing firms in South East Nigeria. The study adopted descriptive survey. The primary source of data was questionnaire. A total population of three hundred and twenty-two (312) staff was used. 273 staff returned the questionnaire. Data was analyzed and Z – test was used to test the hypotheses. Findings showed that Learning and development had positive effect on the increase in revenue, $Z(97, n = 273) = 6.582 < 9.547$. Communication had positive effect on the change in productivity $Z(97, n = 273) = .7.006 < 7.671$. Trusts had positive effect on the reduced expenses $Z(97, n = 273) = .7.671 < 10.107$. The study concluded that learning and development, communication and trust had positive significant effect on the increase in revenue, productivity and reduced expenses. The study recommended that management should ensure and organize frequently training that will help inculcate the values of the organizations in the employees.

There was significant positive relationship between identification of talent and output of food manufacturing firms of Enugu State

Hypotheses two showed the computed ($r = .453 < .985$) is greater than the table value of .000. Therefore, we concluded that there was significant positive relationship between identification of talent and output of food manufacturing firms of Enugu State ($r = .416 < .971$) as reported in the probability value of ($r = .416 < .971, p < .05$). In support of these hypotheses, Aina, and Atan (2020) conducted a study on the Impact of Implementing Talent Management Practices on Sustainable Organizational Performance. As organizations operate in an inexorable marketplace, there are always new and unpredictable difficulties that make managerial roles harder and the achievement of organizational goals and objectives more critical. Recently, the implementation of talent management practices in achieving sustainable organizational performance that will match the firms' operational and strategic goals have been the concern of both academics and practitioners, but the issue has not been exhaustively investigated. The results of this study show that talent attraction and talent retention had no impact on the sustainable organizational performance, whereas learning and development and career management were found to have significantly positive impacts. The study suggests that learning and development, and employee career management, should be leveraged on by the management by concentrating on the coaching and training programs and job rotation so that the firm can achieve sustainable organizational performance.

Conclusion

The study concluded that engaged employees and talent had significant positive relationship with the profitability and output of food beverage manufacturing firms of Enugu State. Employees have special protections, as well as certain obligations, compared to other kinds of workers. Both employees and the organisation benefit from successful performance evaluations. They promote a common understanding of individual needs, work objectives, and standards of acceptable performance. They also give employees and managers a useful tool to aid in employee and organizational development. A well-designed performance evaluation system also can encourage individuals to work together as a team.

Recommendation

The study recommends the following

- i. Learning and development, and employee career management, should be leveraged on by the management by concentrating on the coaching and training programs and job rotation so that the firm can achieve sustainable organizational performance.
- ii. Job allocation in the organization should be according competence and capability.

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